

Thioglycolate Complexes of Trivalent Lanthanum, Cerium, Praseodymium, Neodymium, Samarium, Gadolinium, Terbium, Dysprosium, Holmium, Erbium, Thulium, Ytterbium and Lutetium

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The formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes of rare earth ions ($\text{Ln}^{III} = \text{La}^{III}, \text{Ce}^{III}, \text{Pr}^{III}, \text{Nd}^{III}, \text{Sm}^{III}, \text{Gd}^{III}, \text{Tb}^{III}, \text{Dy}^{III}, \text{Ho}^{III}, \text{Er}^{III}, \text{Tm}^{III}, \text{Yb}^{III}$ and Lu^{III}) with thioglycolic acid (H_2TG) have been studied *pH*-metrically. The equilibrium for the reactions,

A review¹ of rare earth complexes and thioglycolate complexes^{2,3} of the type $\text{Ln}(\text{HSCH}_2\text{COO})_2^+$ and $\text{LnL}_n(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ have been reported earlier. The present communication reports the determination of formation constants of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 rare earth thioglycolate complexes at low *pH* and their dissociation to other complexes at higher *pH* by *pH* measurement method.

Experimental

Rare earth nitrates, 99.99% pure, were used. *pH* titrations were carried out at $32 \pm 1^\circ$ with a ECI-822A digital *pH* meter in nitrogen atmosphere and at 0.1 *M* ionic strength (KNO_3).

Results and Discussion

Determination of formation constants of 1 : 1 rare earth thioglycolate complexes : The reaction taking place (Fig. 1) due to the interaction of the rare earth ions with the thioglycolic acid can be represented as

Where C is the complex formed and n is the number of protons liberated per g-atom of rare earth metal ions. The values of n are calculated by the method followed in the cadmium citrate complex⁴ by using pK_1 and pK_2 values of thioglycolic acid⁵ as 3.58 and 9.78, respectively. The values of n are > 1 beyond *pH* 5.0, 4.8, 4.6, 4.6, 4.6, 4.6, 4.8, 4.8, 4.6, 4.6, 4.6 and 4.4 for $\text{La}^{III} - \text{Lu}^{III}$ systems, respectively. Assuming n to be 1 below these *pH* values, the equilibrium constants (K) for the reaction (1) have been calculated as before^{4,6} and the mean values along with the standard deviations are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF 1 : 1 AND 1 : 2 RARE EARTH THIOLYCOLATE COMPLEXES AT $32 \pm 1^\circ$ AND AT 0.1 *M* IONIC STRENGTH (KNO_3)

Cation M^{3+}	1 : 1 complex		1 : 2 complex	
	$-\log K$	$-\log K_1$	$-\log K^*$	$-\log K_1^*$
La	2.02 ± 0.08	7.25 ± 0.08	3.68 ± 0.11	7.32 ± 0.14
Ce	1.86 ± 0.08	6.80 ± 0.13	3.52 ± 0.09	6.92 ± 0.12
Pr	1.76 ± 0.06	6.61 ± 0.14	3.46 ± 0.11	6.79 ± 0.15
Nd	1.72 ± 0.06	6.55 ± 0.14	3.40 ± 0.11	6.73 ± 0.14
Sm	1.67 ± 0.06	6.44 ± 0.09	3.32 ± 0.12	6.61 ± 0.16
Gd	1.92 ± 0.07	6.71 ± 0.12	3.43 ± 0.12	6.78 ± 0.15
Tb	1.86 ± 0.08	6.81 ± 0.10	3.47 ± 0.09	6.76 ± 0.13
Dy	1.87 ± 0.08	6.81 ± 0.08	3.45 ± 0.11	6.79 ± 0.16
Ho	1.90 ± 0.10	6.87 ± 0.09	3.48 ± 0.10	6.58 ± 0.12
Er	1.80 ± 0.08	6.63 ± 0.05	3.37 ± 0.13	6.67 ± 0.11
Tm	1.71 ± 0.09	6.53 ± 0.07	3.36 ± 0.11	6.58 ± 0.14
Yb	1.65 ± 0.09	6.43 ± 0.06	3.33 ± 0.11	6.53 ± 0.15
Lu	1.60 ± 0.10	6.33 ± 0.10	3.27 ± 0.09	6.43 ± 0.14

In the *pH* ranges, 5.20-7.72, 5.00-7.37, 4.70-7.16, 4.80-7.00, 4.80-6.70, 4.80-6.95, 5.00-6.73, 5.00-6.66, 5.00-6.50, 4.80-5.95, 4.80-6.50, 4.80-6.17, and 4.60-6.30 for $\text{La}^{III} - \text{Lu}^{III}$ systems, respectively n is > 1 but < 2. Hence, in these *pH* ranges the complex, C^{2+} , dissociates to C^+ and a proton.

The equilibrium constants (K_1) of the reaction (2) have been calculated as before^{4,6} and the mean values along with the standard deviations have been recorded in Table 1. The hydroxides of the metals are precipitated at *pH* 7.72, 7.37, 7.16, 7.00, 6.70, 6.95, 6.73, 6.66, 6.50, 5.95, 6.50, 6.17, and 6.30 for $\text{La}^{III} - \text{Lu}^{III}$ systems, respectively.

Determination of formation constants of 1 : 2 rare earth thioglycolate complexes : The reaction taking place (Fig. 2) in the formation of 1 : 2 thioglycolate

Fig. 1. pH titration of 50.00 ml solution containing 5.0×10^{-2} g-mole potassium nitrate and 3.125×10^{-4} g-mole thioglycolic acid (curve A) and that of the same volume of other solutions each containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 2.5×10^{-4} g-mole of trivalent rare earth nitrate, against 0.1 M sodium hydroxide, (B₁) La, (B₂) Ce, (B₃) Pr, (B₄) Nd, (B₅) Sm, (B₆) Gd, (B₇) Tb, (B₈) Dy, (B₉) Ho, (B₁₀) Er, (B₁₁) Tm, (B₁₂) Yb and (B₁₃) Lu.

Fig. 2. pH titration of 50.00 ml solution containing 5.0×10^{-2} g-mole potassium nitrate and 5.65×10^{-4} g-mole thioglycolic acid (curve A), and that of the same volume of other solutions each containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 2.5×10^{-4} g-mole of trivalent rare earth nitrate, against 0.1 M sodium hydroxide, (B₁) La, (B₂) Ce, (B₃) Pr, (B₄) Nd, (B₅) Sm, (B₆) Gd, (B₇) Tb, (B₈) Dy, (B₉) Ho, (B₁₀) Er, (B₁₁) Tm, (B₁₂) Yb and (B₁₃) Lu.

complexes can be represented as

The values of n are calculated as before⁷ by equation (4).

$$\frac{\Delta [\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta [\text{TTG}]}{[\text{Ln}(\text{NO}_3)_3]} = n - 2 a/b \quad (4)$$

Where $a = k_1/[\text{H}^+] + 2k_1k_2/[\text{H}^+]^2$ and $b = 1 + k_1/[\text{H}^+] + k_1k_2/[\text{H}^+]^2$.

Above pH 5.0, 5.0, 4.8, 4.8, 4.8, 4.8, 4.8, 4.8, 4.8, 4.8, and 4.6, respectively for La^{III}-Lu^{III} systems, the values of n are > 2 . Below these pH values two protons are liberated. The equilibrium constants (K^*) for the reaction (3) have been calculated and the mean values along with the standard deviations are tabulated in Table 1.

In the pH ranges 5.20-7.72, 5.20-7.37, 5.00-7.16, 5.00-6.98, 5.00-6.70, 5.00-6.93, 5.00-6.73, 5.00-6.65, 5.00-6.50, 5.00-5.95, 5.00-6.50, 5.00-6.17, and 4.80-6.30 for La^{III}-Lu^{III} systems, respectively the n values are > 2 but < 3 . So, in these pH ranges the complex, C_{1,2}⁺ dissociates to C_{1,2} and H⁺ according to equation (5).

The equilibrium constants (K^*) of reaction (5) have been calculated as before⁴ and the mean values along with the standard deviations are given in Table 1. The relative order of stability is in accordance with the earlier observations¹.

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